

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MANDATORY HOURS OF WORK AND REST ONBOARD CONTAINER SHIPS

Capt. Gilbert Lugtu Castro and Loren Mae M. Naquita, Ph.D.

Philippine Merchant Marine Academy, Graduate School, Manila, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12098752>

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine how the required hours of work and rest on container ships were implemented. It intends to boost productivity and enhance the working conditions and well-being of seafarers regarding rest and work hours with respect to Maritime Labour Convention (MLC) 2006. It employed quantitative and qualitative-descriptive methods, leveraging the strengths to comprehensively address the objectives. The study found that as age increases, the perceived impact of factors on mandatory hours of work and rest decreases slightly. However, factors such as position on board, license acquired, length of sea service, and length of service on container ships have a negative correlation with these challenges. The study identified operational demands, heavy workloads, multiple responsibilities, work and rest hours data recording errors, insufficient communication with ship management, inadequate staffing levels, poorly planned crew rotations, and unexpected circumstances disrupting scheduled work and rest periods. However, age was not found to be a significant influencing factor in these challenges. The findings suggest that age may not be a significant influencing factor in the perceived challenges associated with mandatory hours of work and rest. To improve implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest on container ships, the following are recommended: adding crew, implementing proper planning and management, ensuring a backup system for duty rotation, amending policies under the Maritime Labour Convention 2006, arranging hotel accommodations during port operations, and ensuring sufficient crew for maintenance during passages and port activities, possibly by arranging rider ship maintenance and repair personnel.

Key Words: *container ship, implementation of hours work and rest, Maritime Labour Convention 2006, Filipino seafarers, rights of seafarers*

INTRODUCTION

Seafaring ranks as a highly rewarding and sought-after career among Filipinos, notably those engaged in sea-based occupations. In fact, the Philippines emerges as a principal labor source for international maritime vessels, providing significant economic benefits to the families of Filipino seafarers. This important contribution is highlighted by the UNCTAD's Review of Maritime Transport (2021), which recognizes the Philippines as the global leader in supplying both officers and seafarers to the worldwide maritime industry. According to research conducted by the Institute of Developing Economies in 2018, the Philippines, the country that supplies the research greatest number of seafarers worldwide, is crucial to the supply of seafarers.

In the maritime industry, protecting the health and safety of seafarers is essential. Since the maritime work is physically demanding and requires long hours, it is vital to create guidelines to safeguard the wellness of crew members. The maritime sector has long understood how weariness impairs sailors' performance and attentiveness, endangering overall safety on board. In the past, the sector has often struggled with lengthy work hours and erratic schedules, which has resulted in accidents connected to fatigue and decreased productivity among seafarers. International marine organizations have therefore developed policies and agreements to tackle these issues, stressing the significance of enforcing required work and rest hours.

The research study on work and rest hours for crew members on container ships is crucial, given the unique pressures these vessels face in transporting perishable goods. Container ships are among the fastest cargo ships, essential to ensuring that items such as fresh produce, pharmaceuticals, and other time-sensitive goods reach their destinations in optimal condition. This urgency places immense demands on both the ship and its crew, as any delays can lead to significant financial losses and wasted resources due to spoilage. Effective management of crew work and rest hours is therefore, essential to maintaining the high operational standards required for these fast-paced journeys. Fatigue is a well-documented risk factor that dramatically increases the likelihood of human errors, which can lead to accidents, mechanical failures, and unanticipated delays. A well-rested crew, on the other hand, is more alert, capable, and better equipped to handle the demands of their roles, ensuring the ship can maintain its schedule and deliver its cargo promptly. This study was focused on analyzing the factors and challenges associated with the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest policies onboard container ships, which are crucial for ensuring the safety, well-being and efficient functioning of seafarers and maritime operations. It is in this context that this research sought to dig into the perceptions and rightful observance in the implementation of the mandatory work and rest hours with reference to MLC 2006 and safeguard the working conditions and welfare of the seafarers for them to remain productive and efficient in their chosen field. It is therefore logical to investigate the working conditions and welfare of the seafarers on board container ships and ensure that the same serves the purpose.

Research Questions

This study was primarily focused on analyzing the factors and challenges in the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest onboard container ships. Specifically, this research study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Rank/Position on Board
 - c. License Acquired
 - d. Length of Sea Service
 - e. Length of Sea service on Container ships
2. How is the mandatory hours of work and rest onboard container ships implemented?
3. What are the factors affecting the implementation of hours of work and rest in accordance to MLC 2006?
4. Is there a significant relationship in the seafarers' responses on the factors affecting the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest when grouped according to profile?
5. What are the challenges in the implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest of the Maritime Labour Convention 2006?
6. Is there a significant relationship in the seafarers' responses on the challenges in the implementation of the hours of work and rest of the MLC, 2006 when grouped according to management, operational and support levels?
7. Based on the result of the study, what can be recommended to improve the implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest of the Maritime Labour Convention (MLC), 2006?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed both quantitative and qualitative-descriptive methods, leveraging the strengths of each to comprehensively address its objectives. Data collection involved administering surveys through questionnaires and conducting semi-structured interviews. The survey questionnaire was designed to be user-friendly and concise, requiring no more than 10 minutes to complete. This research necessitated open and reflexive engagement to gather in-depth perspectives. Consequently, the researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with selected management level officers aboard container ships. The study focused on several key variables: the implementation of hours of work and rest on container ships, factors influencing this implementation, and the challenges encountered in the process.

Sampling Method Used

The primary respondents of the study were the Filipino seafarers who worked on international containers ships for at least 2 years and on vacation during the period of January to March 2024. A non-random sampling technique was used to select the respondents. The sample were classified as purposive as the researcher sought only those seafarers who were on vacation during data gathering and willing to participate in the study. A total of 165 seafarers working in container vessels participated in the survey and 25 of them participated in the semi-structured interview. The number of respondents that were included in the target demographic sample were seafarers from container ships who were available during the data gathering.

Instrumentation

The self – made survey questionnaire was the primary data-gathering tool. The instrument was consisted of four (4) parts namely. Part 1 consists of Personal Information/Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of: Age, Position/Designation, License, Nationality, Educational Attainment, Length of Sea Service, and Length of Sea service on Container ships; Part 2 – Implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest onboard container ships, Part 3 – Factors Affecting the mandatory work hours and hours of work in the MLC 2006 namely: General Information, Conditions of Employment, MLC 2006 Regulation 2.3, Code Standard A2.3 and Guideline B2.3; and Part 4 – Challenges encountered in the mandatory implementation of the mandatory work hours and rest hours of the officers and crew on board container ships. Cronbach Alpha technique was used to validate the contents of the survey questionnaire. Survey questionnaire was validated with the assistance of statistician while the semi-structured interview was validated by the research adviser. The survey questionnaire designed for the seafarers has the following parts: Implementation of Mandatory Hours of Work and Rest with 16 items ($\alpha = .757$), Factors Affecting Implementation of Hours of Work and Rest with 10 items ($\alpha = .716$), and Challenges in the Implementation of Hours of Work and Rest with 10 items ($\alpha = .870$). Table 1 describes the internal consistency for the computed Cronbach's alpha for each part.

Table 1
Cronbach's Alpha Interpretation

Cronbach's Alpha	Internal consistency
$0.9 \leq \alpha$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

Data Gathering Procedures

Before using the survey questionnaire, the researcher sought validation of its content with the assistance of experts through the adviser. The said instrument was pre-tested to a group of ten (10) seafarers, who are also connected in the seafaring industry with a minimum of two (2) years working on container ships but were excluded as respondents of the study. The researcher obtained the necessary permission to conduct the survey from the management of the shipping company involved in the study. This step was essential to ensure that the study complied with all regulatory and ethical standards. The shipping company operates a fleet of 38 container ships, providing a substantial base of operations for the survey. To collect data, the researcher employed purposive sampling, a method chosen for its effectiveness in targeting specific, relevant populations. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed to crew members and management, yielding 165 responses. This achieved an impressive 82.5% retrieval rate, indicative of robust participant engagement and effort by the researcher. It was important for the integrity of the study that each of the 38 container ships was represented, ensuring comprehensive data coverage across the company's operations. To collect this data, significant efforts were made to ensure the highest possible response rate. The researcher established multiple channels of communication, followed up with potential respondents, and provided clarifying information as needed to guarantee thorough participation. In addition to the survey, semi-structured interviews were conducted to 25 selected management-level officers. Selection criteria were based on availability and willingness to engage in open, candid discussions about the implementation of hours of work and rest on their respective ships. These interviews provided invaluable qualitative data, enriching the overall findings of the study. Each interview was meticulously planned to draw out detailed and relevant information regarding implementation of work and rest schedules.

Data Analysis

The questionnaires were retrieved online, tabulated and tallied through the assistance of the statistician, which were then analyzed and interpreted. To characterize and describe the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of age, position on board, license, length of sea service and length of sea service on container ships, the frequency count, percentage distribution and average mean were used. Weighted mean was employed in describing the perspectives of the respondents on the different factors affecting the implementation of the work and rest hours on board container ships. Finally, the obtained Weighted Means were treated using the arbitrary 4-Point Likert scale, as follows.

Rating	Scale	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree

To analyze and examine the significant relationship about the perspectives of the informants on the implementation of the mandatory work and rest hours, when grouped according to age, position on board, license, length of sea service and length of sea service on container ships, the study made use of the Pearson Correlation coefficient, particularly in the interpretation of data, as follows:

Table 2
Guidelines for Interpreting Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)

Strength of Relationship Between Variables	Positive	Negative
Weak	.10 to .29	-.10 to -.29
Moderate	.30 to .49	-.30 to -.49
Strong	.50 to 1.00	-.50 to -1.00

RESULTS

There were 165 respondents in this study. They are all Filipino seafarers on board container ships with a minimum of 2 years of experience. Table 3 presents the profiles of the respondents according to age. As seen from the table, 43 out of the 165 of the respondents, which is 26.06 % of the total respondents, belong to the age bracket of 26-30. On the other hand, 35 or 21.21% of the respondents belong to the age bracket of 36-40. This is followed by 34 or 20.61% belonging to the age bracket of 31-35 years old. The least number of the respondents belong to the age bracket of 56-60 which has 2 or 1.21% of the total respondents. Majority of the respondents belong to ages 26 – 30 years old. This is contrary to the study of Pauksztat, et. al. (2021) that the average age of the seafarers is 40 years old. However, the minimum age requirement of the seafarers had been complied as per MLC 2006, Regulation 1.1 which is not less than 18 years of age in this research study.

Table 3
 Respondent's Age

AGE	f	%
21-25	6	3.64%
26-30	43	26.06%
31-35	34	20.61%
36-40	35	21.21%
41-45	16	9.70%
46-50	24	14.55%
51-55	5	3.03%
56-60	2	1.21%

n	165	100.00%
---	-----	---------

Table 4 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of rank or position on board container ships. As seen from the table, 26 or 15.76% of the respondents are able-bodied seamen (AB), which belong to the support level. This is followed by 3rd officers with 12 or 7.27% of the participants belong to the operational level. This is followed by Bosun with 11 or 6.67% of the respondents, which is on the support level. The least number of the respondents belong to the Steward department, which has only one (1) participant or 0.61% of the total number of respondents. This means that majority of the seafarers on board container ships are able-bodied seamen. According to the information published by Liveseas in 2024, the maritime industry is an intricate network of operations, and at the heart of these operations lie the tireless Able Seamen (AB). These individuals form the backbone of most deck crews, ensuring that our ships sail smoothly and safely across the seven seas. This comprehensive overview unravels the various facets of the Able Seaman role, shedding light on their responsibilities, challenges, and the overall career path. The role of an Able Seaman (AB) is both versatile and integral. The AB is the all-rounder of the ship's crew, adept at a range of tasks that ensure smooth operations at sea. Their responsibilities extend from the deck to the bridge, alternating every fortnight, making their role dynamic and indispensable. Hence, more ABs are needed on board ships. Moreover, the ratings or those under the support levels are the most affected group in the observance of hours of work and rest since they are the ones doing the leg works and related jobs. This was confirmed in the unstructured interview with the respondents.

Table 4
Rank/Position Onboard

RANK/ POSITION ONBOARD	f	%
Management Level		
Master	8	4.85%
Chief Officer	7	4.24%
Chief Engineer	5	3.03%
2nd Engineer	5	3.03%
Operational Level		
2nd Officer	9	5.45%
3rd Officer	12	7.27%
3rd Engineer	6	3.64%
4th Engineer	4	2.42%
Electro-Technical Officer	5	3.03%
Support Level		
Deck Ratings		
Bosun	11	6.67%

Able-Bodied Seaman	26	15.76%
Ordinary Seaman	19	11.52%
Engine Ratings		
Wiper/Motorman	9	5.45%
Oiler	20	12.12%
Fitter	2	1.21%
Ratings		
Chief Cook	10	6.06%
Messman	6	3.64%
Steward	1	0.61%
n	165	100.00%

Table 5 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of licenses acquired. They were further classified into management, operational and support levels accordingly. As seen from the table, 35 or 21.21% of the participants did not specify their licenses acquired. This is followed by those who are complied with Regulation II-5 (Deck) with 27 or 16.36% of the total respondents. This means that they had been certified to follow the minimum requirements of having been trained as deck officer prior to boarding ships or boarded ships with 500 gross tonnage and above as minimum requirements. Next to the highest number of respondents are with Officer-in-Charge (OIC)-Navigational Watch (Deck) License with 22 or 13.33% of the total number of respondents. The least number of licenses from the participants are Registered Master Electrician and Electrical Engineer, which both have 1 or 0.61% of the total number of respondents. There were 35 or 21.21% of the respondents have either no license or did not specify at all. These licenses are major considerations in relations their employment conditions regarding the positions, designations and responsibilities attributed to the seafarers. This is also an important factor in the determination of their financial remunerations and related benefits to their employment contracts. Moreover, all these information could be referred to the standard terms and conditions governing the employment of Filipino seafarers on-board Ocean-going vessels. This was also confirmed in the unstructured interview with the respondents.

Table 5
Licenses Acquired

LICENSE ACQUIRED	f	%
Management Level		
Master License	10	6.06%
Chief Officer License	6	3.64%
Chief Engineer License	10	6.06%
2nd Engineer License	1	0.61%
Operational Level		

OIC-Navigational Watch	22	13.33%
OIC-Engineering Watch	13	7.88%
Registered Master Electrician	1	0.61%
Registered Electrical Engineer	1	0.61%
Support Level		
II-4 Deck AB	9	5.45%
II-5 Deck AB	27	16.36%
III-4 Engine	5	3.03%
III-5 Engine	11	6.67%
ETO License	3	1.82%
Ship Catering NC I (Messman)	3	1.82%
Ship Catering NC III (Cook)	8	4.85%
None (or did not specify)	35	21.21%
n	165	100.00%

Table 6 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of length of sea Service in years. As seen from the table, 8 or 41.21% of the respondents belong to the group of those with 6-10 years of experience on board. This is followed by those who belong to 1-5 years of experience with 48 or 28.48% of the total number of respondents. Twenty-eight (28) or 16.97% belong to those with 11-15 years of shipboard experience. Only two (2) or 1.21% of the participants have one (1) or less number of years of experience at sea. This can be aligned with the BIMCO (2021) which states that the demographic profile for STCW-certified ratings shows that while 75% of Indian seafarers are aged between 21 and 40, significant proportions of Ukrainian, Chinese, and Filipino seafarers fall within the 51-60 age bracket. Data for management level officers (master, chief officer, chief engineer, second engineer), operational level officers, and support level ratings shows ages have all increased in 2015. The International Chamber of Shipping's most recent Seafarer Workforce Report (ICS, 2021) confirmed and found the following distinctions between seafarer age profiles and nationality: Largest proportion of officers aged between 21 and 30 are Indians, Largest proportion between 31 and 40 are Chinese, Most Filipino officers are aged over 41, Almost a quarter of Russian officers are over 50 years of age.

Table 6
Length of Sea Service

NO. OF YEARS IN SEA SERVICE	f	%
< 1	2	1.21%
1-5	47	28.48%
6-10	68	41.21%

11-15	28	16.97%
16-20	10	6.06%
21-25	4	2.42%
26-30	6	3.64%
n	165	100.00%

Table 7 presents the length of sea service of the respondents on container ships. Majority of the seafarers on board container ships are within 6 -10 years on board. It could be gleaned from the table that 69 or 41.82% of the respondents belong to those with 6-10 years of experience on container ships. This is followed by those with 1-5 years of experience on board container ships with 49 or 29.7% of the total number of respondents. While 29 or 17.58% of the respondents are with 11-15 years of sea service on container ships. The least number of sea experience onboard container ships belong to those with 21-25 years sea service with only 1 or 0.61% of the total respondents.

Table 7
Length of Sea Service on Container Ships

LENGTH OF SEA SERVICE	f	%
< 1	13	7.88%
1-5	49	29.7%
6-10	69	41.82%
11-15	29	17.58%
16-20	4	2.42%
21-25	1	0.61%
n	165	100%

Interview Respondents Profile

Table 8 presents the profile of the interview respondents in terms of position, and all are management level officers. They were purposively chosen by the researcher since they are the most senior in terms of length of service and had vast experiences on ships, specifically on-board container ships. As seen from the table, eight (8) or 32.0% are masters followed by seven (7) Chief Officers or 28.0% of the total number of respondents. Both the Chief Engineer and the Second Engineers got five (5) each or 0.20% of the total respondents.

Table 8
Interview Respondents Profile

Interviewee	f	%
Management Level		
Master	8	32.0%
Chief Officer	7	28.0%
Chief Engineer	5	20.0%
2nd Engineer	5	20.0%
Total	25	100%

DISCUSSION

Table 9 presents the status of the implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest on board container ships. As seen from the table, the respondents strongly disagree on the item on a table of shipboard working arrangements of rest hours and work hours are in the international working language in English (item no.1) which means that it is fully implemented. The rest of the items (items no. 2-12) belong to the group where the respondents agree, which means that those are being implemented and observed. To wit: the maximum hours of work or minimum hour of rest are also included in the table of shipboard working arrangement; enough time for meals is provided to the crew, e.g. 1 hour for main meals; additional measures or initiatives onboard by the Master, Chief Officer and Chief Engineer to promote the well-being and work-life balance of seafarers; the master exercise his overriding authority to suspend the work schedule in the event of emergency where the safety of the ship and crew are in danger; musters and all drills take place with minimal disturbance to periods of rest; normal working hours are based on an eight-hour day with one day rest per week; Working and rest hours are recorded on board, and each crew member receives a copy; records are being checked and observed by Chief Officer and Chief Engineer to ensure effective compliance with MLC 2006 regulations; the ship's flag registry verifies that the ship is in compliance to work hours and rest hours period of the crew under the regulations of MLC 2006 regulation A 2.3 and B 2.3.1 and the Planned Schedule at sea is being observed and followed in accordance with shipboard working arrangements under the MLC 2006 regulation. The respondents disagree on the item on the Planned Schedule at ports is being observed and followed in accordance with shipboard working arrangements under the MLC 2006 regulations. The items (number 13-15): a 30-minutes break every after two (2) hours of work onboard the ship is allowed, the ship flag registry under which the ships operate provide maximum allowable work hours and sufficient rest hours period under MLC 2006 regulations and the crew work more than 72 hours at any seven-day period are all rated by the respondents and agreed upon as being implemented and observed on board container ships. However, the respondents strongly disagree on the item on the crew works more than 14 hours in any 24-hour period was described by the respondents as not being implemented and observed. Majority of the items were agreed by the respondents as being implemented. However, this also means that there were crucial

items on the mandatory implementation of hours of work and rest in container ships noted and need some attention. This was supported by Graham and Walters (2020) who had stressed that the seafarer’s bill of rights provides a firm but flexible response to poor working conditions in global shipping. Hence, the MLC 2006 and STCW required conditions are strictly adhered to and how the standards are to be met. This is to ensure that seafarers have adequate work and rest periods for them to be more productive and for them to enjoy their work on board. Similarly, the work of Bhatia (2019) claimed that there is an imbalance of the workloads and manning levels on ships. Moreover, companies send report for them to disregard any appeal from the seafarers to address a lack of manning on board. Finally, the respondents report that the maritime industry lacked commitment to deal with fatigue which is a vital consideration for the working conditions of the seafarers” productivity and well-being of the seafarers.

Table 9
Implementation of Mandatory Hours of Work and Rest Onboard Container Ships

INDICATORS	MEAN	VI
1. A table of shipboard working arrangements of rest hours and work hours are in the international working language in English.	3.68	Strongly Agree
2. Maximum hours of work or minimum hour of rest are also included in the table of shipboard working arrangement.	3.22	Agree
3. Enough time for meals is provided to the crew, e.g. 1 hour for main meals.	3.21	Agree
4. Additional measures or initiatives onboard by the Master, Chief Officer and Chief Engineer to promote the well-being and work-life balance of seafarers.	3.20	Agree
5. The master exercise his overriding authority to suspend the work schedule in the event of emergency where the safety of the ship and crew are in danger.	3.19	Agree
6. Musters and all drills take place with minimal disturbance to periods of rest.	3.04	Agree
7. Normal working hours are based on an eight-hour day with one day rest per week.	2.63	Agree
8. Working and rest hours are recorded on board, and each crew member receives a copy.	2.58	Agree
9. Records are being checked and observed (Observance and Implementation) by Chief Officer and Chief Engineer to ensure effective compliance with MLC 2006 regulations.	2.57	Agree
10. The ship’s flag registry verifies that the ship is in compliance to work hours and rest hours period of the	2.55	Agree

crew under the regulations of MLC 2006 regulation A 2.3 and B 2.3.1(Monitoring)

11. The Planned Schedule at sea is being observed and followed in accordance with shipboard working arrangements under the MLC 2006 regulations.	2.53	Agree
12. The Planned Schedule at ports is being observed and followed in accordance with shipboard working arrangements under the MLC 2006 regulations.	2.53	Agree
13. A 30-minute break every after 2 hours of work on board the ship is allowed.	2.48	Disagree
14. The crew work more than 72 hours in any seven-day period.	1.81	Disagree
15. The crew work more than 14 hours in any 24-hour period.	1.65	Strongly Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	2.68	Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 — Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.24 — Agree; 1.75 – 2.49 — Disagree. 1.00 – 1.74 —Strongly Disagree; VI – Verbal Interpretation

Table 10 presents the factors affecting the implementation of hours of work and rest periods according to the perspectives of the seafarer respondents. All the items (no. 1-6) were rated and described by the respondents as Strongly Agree. To wit: Adverse weather conditions, rough seas, or situations requiring extra attention and effort; Ships stay one day at port and after completion of loading and discharge of cargoes operations in port.; Unpredictable port operations, delays, and extended waiting time for berthing; Tight voyage schedules and time constraints; Business Pressures (these are commercial pressures to meet delivery deadlines, maximize efficiency, and reduce costs may prioritize work completion over crew rest requirements) and Insufficient crew members. On the other hand, Items 7 and 8 on the ship Design and Technology: Inadequate accommodation facilities, noise levels, vibration, and ergonomic factors and Poor communication between the crew and shore-based management were rated by the respondents as Agree. The items no. 9 and 10 on rest period of crew are strictly observed and the extent to which ship's flag registry effectively monitor and enforce the implementation of work and rest hours onboard the ship was rated by the respondents as Disagree. The respondents Agree on majority of the items. This means that the respondents generally agreed to the items on the factors affecting the implementation of hours of work and rest in accordance with MLC 2006. Medani (2024), stated that a seafarer also has a right to safe working and living conditions. The ILO's Convention and Protocol establish minimum labour standards for seafarers on merchant vessels. Significantly, it introduced the initiative of port state control in ensuring compliance with these standards; a concept which is duplicated in Regulation is particularly important to seafarers as it requires flag states to guarantee their vessels meet safety standards,

satisfy conditions of employment on these vessels and further that these vessels comply with ILO standards while mandating port states to verify compliance through inspection methods. The minimum requirement for seafarers to work on a ship are summarized into four parts, which are age requirements, medical prerequisites, training and recruitment/placement services. It states that seafarers must be medically fit, with a certificate issued by an approved doctor for duties that they will be assigned onboard as per STCW. As per the medical standards of MLC 2006, most of the ratified countries are providing a medical certificate with an average validity of 2 years. As all concerned are cognizant of the fact that the STCW regulations and medical standards specified within for seafarers are the same anywhere in the world, yet the medical issued by one nation is not accepted by another nation or company when a seafarer is switching companies, but still holds a valid MLC ratified country's medical certificate. For example, a medical certificate issued to an Indian seafarer in Malaysia as per STCW regulations is not accepted while joining another shipping company in the UAE, whose recruitment placement service provider in India needs an Indian directorate general of shipping approved medical certificate to be uploaded in the DGS website. When all the regulations can be traced back to IMO & ILO, and regulation applies to seafarers are same for all, irrespective of the geographic location of the seafarer, why is it that a seafarer must undergo medical, just because of proper lack of implementation and lack of countries trust on each other's administration. Many seafarers have undergone this situation, but as there is no way around it, seafarers must follow the rules. To encounter this predicament, it must consider creating an international format and recognition of doctors and clinics internationally to carry out medical examination for seafarers, which would be valid and acceptable worldwide within the prescribed validity period. This will at the least tackle one of the predicaments confronted by the seafaring community. This is also a logical consideration on the conduct of the study about the implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest on board container ships.

Table 10
Factors Affecting the Implementation of Hours of Work and Rest

FACTORS	MEAN	VI
1. Adverse weather conditions, rough seas, or situations requiring extra attention and effort	3.57	Strongly Agree
2. Ships stay one day at port and after completion of loading and discharge of cargoes operations in port.	3.55	Strongly Agree
3. Unpredictable port operations, delays, and extended waiting time for berthing	3.48	Strongly Agree
4. Tight voyage schedules and time constraints	3.45	Strongly Agree
5. Business Pressures (these are commercial pressures to meet delivery deadlines, maximize efficiency, and reduce costs may	3.35	Strongly Agree

prioritize work completion over crew rest requirements)

6. Insufficient crew members	3.28	Strongly Agree
7. Ship Design and Technology: Inadequate accommodation facilities, noise levels, vibration, and ergonomic factors	3.05	Agree
8. Poor communication between the crew and shore-based management	2.93	Agree
9. Rest periods of crew are strictly observed and implemented as per schedule.	2.47	Disagree
10. The extent to which ship's flag registry effectively monitor and enforce the implementation of work and rest hours onboard the ship.	2.45	Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	3.16	Agree

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 — Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.24 — Agree; 1.75 – 2.49 — Disagree; 1.00 – 1.74 — Strongly Disagree; VI – Verbal Interpretation

The results presented in Table 11 reveal some correlation between the factors affecting the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest, particularly when grouped by respondents' profile characteristics. When examining the respondents' age, a statistically significant weak, negative correlation emerged ($r = -.175$, $p = .025$). This suggests that as age increases, there is a tendency for a slight decrease in the perceived impact of these factors on the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest. Secondly, when considering the respondents' position onboard, a similar weak, negative correlation was observed ($r = -.228$, $p = .003$). This implies that individuals in different positions onboard exhibit varying perspectives of the influence of these factors, with a slight decrease in correlation as the position onboard changes. Furthermore, the length of sea service also demonstrated a statistically significant weak, negative correlation ($r = -.241$, $p = .002$). This implies that individuals with different lengths of sea service hold distinct perspectives on the factors affecting the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest, with a minor decline in correlation as the length of sea service increases. In contrast, no statistically significant relationship was found between these factors and the respondents' length of sea service onboard container ships ($r = -.133$, $p = .089$), suggesting that this specific variable may not strongly influence perspectives regarding mandatory hours of work and rest in the context of container ships.

Table 11

Correlation Analysis of Profile with the Factors Affecting the Implementation of Mandatory Hours of Work and Rest

PROFILE		
1. Age:	Correlation	-.175*
	Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	
2. Position Onboard:	Correlation	-.228**
	Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	
3. License Acquired	Correlation	-1.60
	Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	
3. Length of Sea Service:	Correlation	-.241**
	Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	
4. Length of Sea Service Onboard Container Ships:	Correlation	-.133
	Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	

Note: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 12 presents the challenges in the implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest onboard container ships. As seen from the table, the respondents Strongly Agree on all the items 1-7 as follows: Operational demands that require to work beyond the prescribed hours; Heavy workload at port activities and tight schedules between ports; Multiple responsibilities, which can make it challenging to track and limit the working hours effectively; Work and rest hours data recording and documentation errors; Insufficient communication or consultation with the ship's management; Inadequate staffing levels or poorly planned crew rotations and Unforeseen circumstances disrupting scheduled work and rest periods. However, the item on unbalanced distribution of workload among the crew members (No. 8), the respondents Agree. On the other hand, the items on cultural norms or social expectations that encourage longer working hours and Inadequate onboard accommodations, such as cramped or uncomfortable living quarters, that leads to lack of enough rest, where the respondents Disagree. This means that the last 2 items described have not been regarded by the respondents as a challenge in the mandatory implementation of the hours of work and rest as per regulation of MLC 2006. Majority of

the items on the Challenges in the Implementation of the Mandatory Hours of Work and Rest of the MLC 2006 had been agreed by the respondents, except on the noted items which the respondents disagree such as cultural norms or social expectations that encourage longer working hours and inadequate onboard accommodations, such as cramped or uncomfortable living quarters, that leads to lack of enough rest. As a result, the following are the identified challenges as a result of the study: 1. Operational demands that require to work beyond the prescribed hours, 2. Heavy workload at port activities and tight schedules between ports, 3. Multiple responsibilities, which can make it challenging to track and limit the working hours effectively, 4. Work and rest hours data recording and documentation error, 5. Insufficient communication or consultation with the ship's management, 6. Inadequate staffing levels or poorly planned crew rotations, and 7. Unforeseen circumstances disrupting scheduled work and rest periods. All these items were confirmed by the respondents in the semi-structured interview.

Table 12
Challenges in the Implementation of the Mandatory Hours of Work and Rest

CHALLENGES	MEAN	VI
1. Operational demands that require to work beyond the prescribed hours	3.40	Strongly Agree
2. Heavy workload at port activities and tight schedules between ports	3.38	Strongly Agree
3. Multiple responsibilities, which can make it challenging to track and limit the working hours effectively	3.36	Strongly Agree
4. Work and rest hours data recording and documentation errors	3.32	Strongly Agree
5. Insufficient communication or consultation with the ship's management	3.28	Strongly Agree
6. Inadequate staffing levels or poorly planned crew rotations	3.26	Strongly Agree
7. Unforeseen circumstances disrupting scheduled work and rest periods	3.25	Strongly Agree
8. Unbalanced distribution of workload among the crew members	3.19	Agree
9. Cultural norms or social expectations that encourage longer working hours	2.28	Disagree
10. Inadequate onboard accommodations, such as cramped or uncomfortable living quarters, that leads to lack of enough rest	2.20	Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	3.09	Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 — Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.24 — Agree; 1.75 – 2.49 — Disagree. 1.00 – 1.74 — Strongly Disagree; VI – Verbal Interpretation

Table 13 shows some existing correlations concerning the challenges encountered in the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest, particularly when grouped according to the respondents' profile characteristics. As for the respondents' position onboard, a statistically significant weak, negative correlation was identified ($r = -.238$, $p = .002$). This suggests that individuals in different roles onboard exhibit varying degrees of correlation with the challenges in implementing mandatory hours of work and rest, indicating a potential impact of position-related factors on the perceived difficulties. Similarly, the License Acquired yielded significantly weak, with negative correlation ($r = -.159$, $p = .077$). This suggests that the various licenses of each of the seafarers exhibits different degrees of correlation with the challenges in implementing mandatory hours of work and rest, which may mean a negative relation on the perceived challenges in the implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest on board container ships. Moreover, the length of sea service displayed a statistically significant weak, negative correlation ($r = -.271$, $p < .001$). This implies that respondents with diverse lengths of sea service experience distinct levels of correlation with the challenges in implementing mandatory hours of work and rest, with a more pronounced decrease in correlation as the length of sea service increases. Lastly, when focusing on the length of sea service onboard container ships, a statistically significant weak, negative correlation was observed ($r = -.167$, $p = .032$). This suggests that individuals with varying lengths of sea service on container ships may perceive different degrees of correlation with the challenges, demonstrating a potential influence of vessel type on these perspectives. However, there was no statistically significant relationship found between these challenges and the respondents' age ($r = -.144$, $p = .066$), indicating that age might not be a substantial influencing factor in the perceived challenges associated with implementing mandatory hours of work and rest.

Table 13
Correlation Analysis of Profile with the Challenges in the Implementation of the Mandatory Hours of Work and Rest

PROFILE		
1. Age:	Correlation Coefficient	-.144
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.066
	N	165
2. Position Onboard:	Correlation Coefficient	-.238**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
	N	165
3. License Acquired	Correlation Coefficient	-1.59
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.077

	N	165
4. Length of Sea Service:	Correlation Coefficient	-.271**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001
	N	165
5. Length of Sea Service Onboard Container Ships:	Correlation Coefficient	-.167*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.032
	N	165

Note: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Result of the Interview

Table 14
Knowledge and understanding of MLC 2006

Questions:	Category/Theme
Q1: Are you provided with a detailed work schedule that clearly outlines your hours of work and rest periods as per MLC 2006 regulations regarding mandatory hours of work and rest onboard container ships? (Yes /No)	Schedule of work and rest
Q2: Have you received on board familiarization training or information on MLC 2006 regulations, pertaining to rest hours and works hours on board (Yes/No)	Familiarization training
Q3: Do you understand the requirements of mandatory rest hours and works hours on board the vessel under MLC 2006 regulations? (Yes/No)	Understanding of the requirements
Summary of Responses: The responses are unanimously affirmative for all the questions. This means that the seafarers are provided with a detailed work schedule of hours of work and rest, had done familiarization training, and had adequate understanding on the implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest on board container ships.	

Table 15
Implementation of Mandatory Hours of Work and Rest

Questions:	Category/Theme
<p>Q4: Are the mandatory hours of work and rest consistently followed on board container ships? (Yes/No)</p> <p>Q5: How often, if any, have you observed instances where the mandatory hours of work and rest were not followed? (4 - Frequently; 3 – Occasionally; 2 – Rarely; 1 – Never)</p> <p>Q6: Are there specific roles or tasks on board that require working beyond the prescribed hours of work and rest?</p>	<p>Consistently followed. Observation</p> <p>Specific roles beyond prescribed</p>
<p>Summary of Responses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The question on consistently followed was answered No. This means that there are cases that some of the schedules are not followed due to unavoidable circumstances beyond control. 2. This also applies to the idea that as per observation there are instances that there are instances that occasionally, hours of work and rest are not followed. 3. Lastly, it was confirmed that there are specific roles or tasks that require working beyond hours of work and rest on board container ships. 	

Table 16
Factors Affecting Implementation

Question:	Category/Theme
<p>Q3: What are the factors affecting the implementation of the mandatory work hours and rest on board container ships?</p>	
<p>Summary of Responses: (These factors are identified by the respondents in the interview and were ranked accordingly).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Insufficient communication or consultation with the ship's management 	<p>Communication gap</p>

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Multiple responsibilities, which can make it challenging to track and limit the working hours effectively. 3. Adverse weather conditions, rough seas or situations requiring extra attention and efforts. 4. Heavy workload at port activities and tight schedules between ports 5. Work and rest hours data recording and documentation errors. 6. Inadequate staffing levels or poorly planned crew rotations 	<p>Heavy work loads</p> <p>Adverse weather conditions Multi-tasking</p> <p>Recording errors</p> <p>Inadequate staff</p>
--	---

Table 17
Challenges in the Implementation

Question:	Category/Theme
<p>Q3: What are the challenges in the implementation of the mandatory work hours and rest on board container ships?</p>	
<p>Summary of Responses: (The following challenged were identified by the respondents)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Operational demands that require to work beyond the prescribed hours. 2. Heavy workload at port activities and tight schedules between ports 3. Multiple responsibilities, which can make it challenging to track and limit the working hours effectively. 4. Unbalanced distribution of workload among the crew members 5. Inadequate onboard accommodations, such as cramped or uncomfortable living quarters, that leads to lack of enough rest. 	<p>Operational demands Heavy work loads</p> <p>Multi-tasking</p> <p>Unbalance distribution. Inadequate accommodation</p>

Table 18
Recommendation to improve implementation.

Question:	Category/Theme
Q4: What measures to you think can be taken to improve the implementation of the mandatory work hours and rest on board container ships?	
<p>Summary of Responses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Additional crew for container ships 2. Charterers and ship owners to arrange a day rest of all officers and crew after each cargo port operation completion and proceed to anchorage. 3. Increase ship manning requirement for each flag state on the vessels. 4. Formulation of company policies to assure proper implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest on container ships. 5. Ensure a backup system for duty rotation to allow crew members to take rest periods, especially during busy schedules or multiple port rotations. 	<p>Additional crew A day rest after operation</p> <p>Safe manning requirements New Company policy Backup system</p>

Conclusions

Findings of the study revealed that as age increases, there is a tendency for a slight decrease in the perceived impact of the factors on the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest. However, the position on board, license acquired, length of sea service and length of service on container ship have negative correlation with the different factors. The results also showed some existing correlations concerning the challenges encountered in the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest, particularly when grouped according to the respondents' profile characteristics. Individuals in different roles onboard exhibit varying degrees of correlation with the challenges in implementing mandatory hours of work and rest, indicating a potential impact of position-related factors on the perceived difficulties. Various licenses of each of the seafarers exhibits different degrees of correlation with the challenges in implementing mandatory hours of work and rest, which may mean a negative relation on the perceived challenges in the implementation of the mandatory hours of work and rest on board container ships.

Moreover, the length of sea service displayed a statistically significant weak, negative correlation and the diverse lengths of sea service experience distinct levels of correlation with the challenges in implementing mandatory hours of work and rest, with a more pronounced decrease in correlation as the length of sea service increases. The length of sea service onboard container ships was found to be statistically significantly weak,

negative correlation was observed that individuals with varying lengths of sea service on container ships may perceive different degrees of correlation with the challenges, demonstrating a potential influence of vessel type on these perspectives.

However, there was no statistically significant relationship found between these challenges and the respondents' age which means that age might not be a substantial influencing factor in the perceived challenges associated with implementing mandatory hours of work and rest. The following were identified challenges as a result of the study: operational demands that require to work beyond the prescribed hours, heavy workload at port activities and tight schedules between ports, multiple responsibilities, which can make it challenging to track and limit the working hours effectively, work and rest hours data recording and documentation error, insufficient communication or consultation with the ship's management, Inadequate staffing levels or poorly planned crew rotations, and unforeseen circumstances disrupting scheduled work and rest periods.

Recommendations

The following are the recommended measures to improve the implementation of mandatory hours of work and rest on board containers ships: consider additional crew onboard to prevent working overload and fatigue, especially after cargo operations, with suggestion for at least one day of rest at anchorage, implement careful planning and management by officers, including proper to anticipate workloads and rest requirements, including proper record-keeping of work and rest hours, ensure a backup system for duty rotation to allow crew members to take rest periods, especially during busy schedules or multiple port rotations, review, amend and adopt policies related to crew working hours and rest periods under the Maritime Labour Convention 2006 to address specific challenges faced by the container ships, arrange hotel accommodations for crew during port operations, allowing at least 24 hours of rest ashore and provide additional compensation for overtime work and ensure sufficient crew on board older ships for adequate maintenance during passages and port activities, possibly by arranging rider ship maintenance and repair personnel.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Given the nature of this study, there are certain ethical declarations that were considered. All respondents were treated with respect and courtesy. The research was conducted using an informed consent, in which all participants were advised about the study's purpose and procedures and consent to record the interview was obtained. The responses of the respondents were treated with confidentiality. When the results are published, no information will be linked to any individual, vessel, or shipping company to assure anonymity of the respondents. Privacy were protected as only those people linked to this research project have access to the collected data. Related literatures and studies were properly cited and reference list to prevent plagiarism.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to offer this piece of work to Almighty God, above all, for His wisdom, and the provision of courage, which have enabled him to pursue this study. He is also indebted to the Philippine Merchant Marine Academy Graduate School under the leadership of Dean Ma. Nissa C. Espiritu MSc and CDR Victoria Q. Paraggua, PhD., together with the other members of the faculty and staff for their motivation. The researcher would like to thank his adviser, Prof. Loren Mae Niquita, PhD; to the members of the oral defense panel: Chairman, Dr. Victoria Q. Paragua, and members: Capt. Vincent Brian P. Conde, Jr. and Capt. Neopol L. Salvador, PhD for their untiring and excellent advises and support for the betterment of this research study; also, to Hon. Atty. Panos Zalachoris and Mr Nikolaos Savvas Owner of Shipping company he works for the opportunity afforded him to conduct the study. To his beloved beautiful wife Miliza M. Castro, and sons Gimil and Gerson, for the moral support and understanding while doing the research study and who served as his inspiration to move on. Lastly, to his Adviser Prof. Loren Mae M. Naquita, PhD, and friends, to them the researcher will forever be grateful.

REFERENCES

- Admin. (2023, September 22). Report Pearson correlation coefficient from SPSS in APA style. EZ SPSS Tutorials. <https://ezspss.com/how-to-report-pearson-correlation-coefficient-from-spss-in-apa-style/>
- An Act Instituting Policies for the Protection and Welfare of Domestic Workers (2013), Republic Act No. 10361
- Bhatia, B. S. (2019), "Exploration of implementation and reporting of hours of work and hours" by Bikram Singh Bhatia (wmu.se)
- Edumaritime.net (2021), Hours of Work and Hours of Rest for Seafarers.
- Graham, C. and Walters, D. (2020), Representation of Seafarer's Occupational Safety and Health: Limits of the Maritime Labour Convention, The Economic and Labor Relations Review
- <https://liveseas.com/navtex/role-of-an-able-seaman-overview>
- Institute of Developing Economies (2018), Filipino seafarers: How the Philippines Emerged as the Largest Supplier of Seafarers in the World (2018_2_40_023) - Institute of Developing Economies (ide.go.jp)
- International Chamber of Shipping, (2021), Shipping and World Trade: Global Supply and Demand for Seafarers | International Chamber of Shipping (ics-shipping.org)
- International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers, 1978 (imo.org) extracted 2024.
- Medani, N. O. (2013), "Assessing the Effectiveness and Efficiency of the Maritime Labour Convention 2006: The Rights of Seafarers to their Wages", www.academia.edu.com
- Paukstat, Birgit (2021), Effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health of seafarers: A comparison using matched samples, PubMed.
- Press Release (2021), Asia expands its lead in maritime trade and business | UNCTAD
- The protection of Seafarers: State Practice and the emerging new International regime (researchgate.net), extracted 2024.